

Significance of Feedback Analysis in Undergraduate Gross Anatomy Teaching

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: Gross anatomy teaching is fundamental in the future learning of clinical subjects in undergraduate medical courses. Students are the most important stakeholders in this process of teaching and learning, so their constant feedback evaluation is essential to construct a comprehensive, clinically oriented, composite gross anatomy curriculum. The present study was carried out to assess and evaluate students' feedback regarding gross anatomy teaching/assessment in CMH Medical College Lahore.

Study design: cross sectional, descriptive studies

Place & duration of study: Conducted in the Anatomy department of CMH Lahore Medical College.

Methods: Present study was based on the observation and analysis of a feedback data. A total of 150 medical students of the first year MBBS class took part in this study. A feedback opinion form was distributed amongst them during the active session. The form comprised of 16 questions, based on the subject matter, instructional methodology, standard of teaching, teaching instruments, modes of assessment used, and students' suggestions for improvement in the current state of gross anatomy teaching.

Results: Although majority (77%) of the students showed interest in the subject and were satisfied with the subject matter, methodology and tools of teaching but a quite reasonable (23%) number of students suggested that audiovisual aids and innovative tools should have been used more. Moreover, they wanted more CBL sessions and clinical visits.

Conclusion: The traditional teaching tools are becoming less affective as well as the new student of modern age becomes more challenging to handle, modification in the courses and redesigning the teaching tools is the need of the hour for an efficacious, balanced gross anatomy course. As there is always a room for improvement, a constant system of feedback analysis can make teaching – learning more conducive to our learning outcomes as well as more fun for students.

Keywords: *Gross Anatomy Teaching, Student's Feedback, Evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Students being the important stake holders in the teaching and learning process should be involved actively in the process of reviewing the teaching and assessment methods in medical education. For this, their feedback analysis needs to be evaluated regularly during the educational process to bring about constructive changes in the current methodology.^{1,2}

Some previous researchers have opinionated that students' judgments are not reliable and valid as they are inconsistent in making opinions and are always looking for an easy way out that suits them, however this opinion has not been supported by later research.^{3,4}

Some studies have compared the ratings of educational activity by students with that by the instructors themselves in order to find out the consistency and reliability of students feedback⁵. There is a moderate correlation of students rating with that of administrators, and also moderate relationship has been shown between the feedback of faculty and students.^{6,7} Moreover it has been found that student age, gender or level of study does not affect their feedback about the teaching/learning process.⁸

Therefore, it can be concluded from these findings that the value and worth of student's opinion is indeed very significant. Critical appraisal of student opinions is imperative, to take the faculty and administration of an educational setup on board, regarding the needs assessment of the students and the positive and negative points of teaching / learning process.^{9,10} Thus, effectiveness of students' reflections in the process of up gradation or change in the curriculum of any study course cannot be undermined.

The present study was carried out to assess and evaluate students' feedback regarding gross anatomy teaching/assessment in CMH Medical College Lahore.

- The purpose of the study was to observe students view point regarding;
- Coverage of gross anatomy subject matter in lectures,
- Suitability of teaching techniques used in gross anatomy,
- Quality of gross anatomy teaching in terms of understanding of concepts of the subject,
- Use of innovative and modern audiovisual teaching tools,
- The tools of assessment used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our study was carried out in the form of a survey quiz in the Anatomy department of CMHLMC & IOD Lahore.

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One hundred and fifty medical students belonging to the first year MBBS class participated in this study. A feedback Performa based on Likert's five points scale was distributed amongst the students, during active teaching session after getting verbal consent from them. Questionnaire is attached as **Table-1**.

The questions in the Performa were based on the coverage of subject matter, teaching techniques, quality of teaching, use of innovative teaching and assessment tools, and their recommendations to enhance the standards of teaching gross anatomy.

The responses obtained from questionnaire were analyzed regarding following attributes:

Coverage of subject matter (Qs 1, 2 & 3)

Quality of teaching (Qs 4, 6 & 16)

Techniques of teaching (Qs 7, 8)

Use of innovative tools (Qs 9- 13)

Modes of assessment of students (Qs 14, 15)

Each attribute was assessed by analysis of responses to the particular questions for that attribute. Response 1 and

2 of each question were gauged together as inadequate or unsatisfactory. Response 3, 4 and 5 were graded together as adequate or satisfactory. Recommendations by the students to enhance the standard of gross anatomy teaching in the last question were discussed as a separate entity.

RESULTS

115 out of 150 students returned back the questionnaire after voluntarily responding to the questions. Student's responses to the feedback form are given in **Table-2**.

Student's Response for the Coverage of course subject matter and Quality of teaching are given in **Figures 1 and 2**.

Student's response for Methodology of teaching, use of innovative tools and mode of assessment for students are shown in **Figures 3-5**.

However, suggestions in response to question number 16 were observed separately and discussed.

Table-1: Student Feedback About Gross Anatomy Teaching And Assessment:

STUDENT'S FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE Please grade the following as; 1-Poor, 2- Fair, 3-Good, 4-Very good, 5-excellent.						
S. No.	Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1	Coverage of important and relevant subject topics in lectures.					
2	Clinical correlation of the topics in lectures was ensured.					
3	Flow of lectures was adequate to explain the concepts of topic					
4	Lectures prompted the students in such a way to promote additional self-study.					
5	Pace of lecture delivery was suitable for the level of student to understand.					
6	Freedom of questioning was given to the students during lectures.					
7	Lectures and demonstrations stimulated interest in the subject.					
8	Session of dissection/prosection with suitable instructions helped in proper identification and study of various structures.					
9	Innovative tools like videos, animations that were included in lectures and demonstrations to help provide understanding of the topic.					
10	CBL sessions helped you to understand and learn the concepts of gross anatomy with clinical relevance.					
11	CBL sessions motivated for self- study and independent learning.					
12	CBL sessions helped improve your communication and presentation skills and confidence.					
13	Clinical visits / skill lab helped increase your interest and motivation for the subject adding clinical flavor.					
14	Assessments conducted in the form of written examinations (multiple choice questions and short answer questions), were enough for ensuring students level of understanding of the subject.					
15	Assessment conducted in the form of viva voce/OSPE examination helped you to assess and improve your core knowledge and its practical application.					
16	What suggestions would you like to give to improve teaching of gross anatomy? Please write in maximum two sentences.					

TABLE-2: Students' responses to the questionnaire as inadequate/dissatisfactory and adequate/satisfactory.

Group	Inadequate/ dissatisfactory % response(1+2)	Adequate/Satisfactory %response(3+4+5)
Coverage of subject matter (Fig.1)	20%	77%
Quality of teaching (Fig.2)	23.5%	77%
Teaching Methodology (Fig. 3)	39%	74%
Innovative Tools used (Fig. 4)	25%	74%
Mode of Assessment (Fig.5)	14%	86%

Content Coverage

Figure-1: Students' response for the coverage of subject matter

Quality of Teaching

Figure-2: Students' response for quality of teaching

Teaching Methodology

Figure-3: Students' response for teaching methodology

Use of Innovative Tools

Figure-4, Students' Response For The Use Of Innovative Tools

Mode of Assessment

Figure-5: Students' Responses For Mode Of Assessment Of Students For Learning Input

DISCUSSION

The use of students' feedback for assessing teaching-learning process has been shown to be very effective and relatively consistent.¹¹ Feedbacks have an added advantage of being easier to obtain and quite inexpensive too.

In the present study, out of 150 students approached for feedback, 115(76%) responded with their opinion. More than 90% response by students has been reported in earlier studies.^{12,13}

In our data, majority of respondents (77% in comparison to 20%) were satisfied with the coverage of subject matter work during lectures. These observations were supported by some previous works who reported that most of their students were content with the coverage of syllabus content, lecture delivery, demonstration of concepts and language used.¹⁴ Another researcher has reported that more than 80% of his students gave positive opinion about the effectiveness of demonstrations and tutorials by teachers.¹⁵ Some investigators have documented that practical demonstrations and hands on skills were more liked by students as they helped better in solving their queries.^{12,13} Another study found that 71.6% learners observed that addition of kinesthetic skills like drawings and figurative illustrations enhanced their conceptual subject understanding.¹⁰

In this study, 77% of the students were happy with the teaching methodology. They were appreciative of method of emphasizing important points and key concepts in large and small group demonstrations during anatomy teaching sessions. Great number of our students were of the opinion that teaching methodology and quality as well as the innovative teaching tools like use of interactive gross anatomy atlases, CBL sessions, and Clinical rounds were much appreciated by them (84%). This is similar to the findings of other researchers in which a great number of students advocated the use of modern audiovisual aids like animations, video clips, as teaching tools, instead of the more orthodox didactic lectures with white/black boards or overhead projectors.^{12,14,15}

In our study, 86% of students didn't have any problem with the present practice of assessment modes in our subject, and this finding is supported by other observers¹⁴ who found out that a great majority of students were of the view that the variety of tools of assessments, including multiple choice questions, short essay questions, viva voce and objectively structured practical examinations etc., enhance their learning and improve their skill.

Individual suggestions in response to question number 16 were broadly as following;

Lectures need to be more interactive involving student participation.

More innovative tools like videos and animations,

dissection videos should be included in lectures.

During dissection/prosection the groups should be small so each student gets ample chance.

Case Based Learning (CBL) sessions and clinical visits should be increased.

Many past studies have reported more or less same suggestions in the students' feedback.^{12,16}

The most frequently raised point by the students in these studies was to lessen boredom and lack of attention span issues in lectures by making them more interactive. More and better use of multimedia, facilitative teaching atmosphere, to hold more CBL sessions and frequent clinical visits were the other suggestion by our students.

Taking into consideration the suggestions of students we have tried to incorporate them in planning next session teaching schedules to have more interactive lectures, more organized dissection/ prosection groups, weekly CBL sessions and clinical lectures and clinical visits of relevant wards in order to make gross anatomy learning more effective, interesting and relevant for students. Moreover the teaching faculty is being encouraged to take more and more training from the medical education in the form of various course and workshops from time for the capacity building of the teaching faculty to improve the performance of the department individually and of the institution as a whole.

Although we do face restraint on account of limited human resource for having very small groups for CBL sessions, we are trying to make maximum and efficient use of existing faculty strength by organizing the sessions a better way. Moreover, efforts are underway to acquire virtual reality software for the teaching of gross anatomy in order to combat scarcity of cadavers in current times.

CONCLUSION

Students are the main stake holders in academic process so their feedback should not be ignored rather it should be taken regularly in order to make the process of teaching and learning more conducive and effective, as their feedback helps us to reflect upon ourselves as faculty. This can help us improve the health care system by producing better trained professionals.

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